

nurse cells (20 mg/ml). Suspension cultures of Oc cell line from Dr. K. Syono of the University of Tokyo were used as nurse cells. Nurse cells were removed after 10 d and the liquid was replaced with the same amount of fresh medium. Under the inverted microscope, the cultures were observed periodically for colony formation. The number of colony-producing protoplasts was recorded 4 wk after plating.

Semisolid N₆ medium consisting of 0.6% agarose VII wt/vol and 2 mg 2,4-D/

liter was tested with sucrose and maltose as the C source. The protoplasts remained viable (with cytoplasmic streaming and changes in shape) for a longer time (3-5 d) in maltose than in sucrose (1-2 d).

We used maltose as the C source when we tested series of semisolid N₆ media. Maltose (13% wt/vol) was found to be the best osmotic concentration for protoplast culture (Table 1). Many cellular divisions and some colonies were

observed 28 d after plating.

To evaluate the efficiency of colony formation, the N₆ medium with 13% maltose was modified using 0.6% agarose VII and 0.5% sea plaque agarose. Both media gave about the same hardness. The plating efficiency was higher in medium with sea plaque agarose (Table 2).

So far, initial attempts to regenerate green plants from protoplast-derived calli have produced only green points. □

Low-light-adapted restorers of different maturity durations for hybrid rice breeding

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Low light levels during the critical reproductive and ripening phases adversely affect rice productivity. Heterotic hybrid combinations with restorers adapted to low light can improve productivity during the wet season (WS).

We studied the low light adaptability of 39 recently purified restorers of elite rice varieties with maturity durations of early (111-120 d), early to medium (121-130 d), medium (131-140 d), and late (more than 141 d). Wooden screens shaded the plants in the field and provided 50% sunlight from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (340 cal/cm² per d).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Yield, total dry matter (TDM), and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest.

The low light reduced mean TDM by 63%, yield 75%, and HI 36% (see table). The extent of reduction, however, was least in the late-maturing group and most in the early to medium group. TDM, yield, and HI were high—specially under low light—iRtb 10, IR50 (early); Swarnaprabha, IR64 R (early to medium); IR19058-107-1, Vajram, ARC11353 (medium); and Jagannath and Mahsuri (late). These restorers also

The effect of low light (50% of normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on yield, TDM, and HI of restorers with varying maturity durations. Cuttack, India, 1991 wet season.

Restorer	Yield (g/m ²)		TDM (g/m ²)		HI (%)	
	Light	Shade	Light	Shade	Light	Shade
Early (111-120 d)						
IR58	437	83	825	286	53	29
WGL3962	413	61	831	206	49	27
IR50	369	113	733	315	50	36
Ptb 10	347	202	669	452	52	45
IR50 R	342	91	701	280	48	32
Prasad	338	44	683	175	49	25
HKR120	334	77	773	303	42	26
IET6155	323	67	620	194	52	34
Semaigincha	320	77	760	233	55	33
IR339515-8-1-1	300	58	602	184	49	32
WGL 3935	256	36	635	194	40	17
IR22107-120-1	231	41	494	144	47	28
Early to medium (121-130 d)						
Swarnaprabha ^a	567	142	1167	481	49	28
IR64 R	392	102	936	350	41	30
Suweon 318	379	38	860	191	44	20
Tellahdmsa	368	32	786	208	49	15
HKR119	365	80	809	242	45	33
IR64	352	61	773	219	46	28
IR36	351	64	133	238	43	27
Suweon 332	338	48	727	198	46	25
Suweon 294	325	68	736	229	44	30
Pusa 702 R	321	74	683	248	47	31
Pusa 205 R	313	40	856	221	36	17
Suweon 325	261	36	590	157	44	23
Milyang 54	235	32	657	164	36	21
Ratna ^a	223	17	681	177	34	17
Medium (131-140 d)						
Vajram	560	150	1409	473	40	34
ARC11353	421	138	1027	488	40	26
IR54	363	111	1094	464	33	23
IR19058-107-1	337	158	1227	595	27	27
Indira ^a	257	56	1047	262	25	19
IR2731.5-145-1-3	257	86	937	470	26	19
Indrasan	249	86	581	289	43	28
IR4422-480-2-3-3	191	24	719	171	26	14
Late (more than 141 d)						
Jagannath	576	219	1366	656	42	33
Mahsuri	475	187	1283	677	37	27
Savitri	469	158	1447	679	49	32
Samalei	460	168	1419	601	32	28
Swama	433	186	1106	523	39	36
LSD (0.05)	162	58	226	129	11	ns
Means						
111-120 d	334	79	694	247	49	30
121-130 d	342	60	785	237	43	25
131-140 d	329	100	1005	401	33	24
>141 d	483	184	1324	627	40	36
General mean	355	90	871	3	2442	27

^aPartial restorer.

recorded less reduction in TDM and yield percentages under low light.

Physiologically efficient restorers, such as IR19058-107-1, Vajram, ARC11353, Jagannath, and Mahsuri, may be effective in developing superior medium- and late-maturing rice hybrids for subdued-light areas. □

Fertility alteration in photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) rice in response to photoperiod and temperature

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The altered fertility of PGMS rice is generally considered to be induced by photoperiod. The sterility of PGMS rice is not always stable during long-day conditions, however, which makes it difficult to use.

We observed the spikelet fertility percentage of the original PGMS line Nongken 58S and of some derived lines under different photoperiod and temperature conditions. We conducted the experiments during 1990 and 1991 by stages. The plants were grown in phytotrons from panicle initiation to heading, about 20-25 d. We observed the fertility percentage 30 d after heading of japonica photoperiod-sensitive sterile lines selfed Nongken 58S and 63343, indica photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines W7415S and W6154S, indica check Guangluai 4, and japonica check Mudanjiang 8 (see table).

Results suggest that there is no absolute photoperiod-sensitive sterility or thermosensitive sterility for fertility induction in the sterile lines from Nongken 58S. The fertility alteration of PGMS rice is regulated by both photoperiod and temperature conditions and is a result of interaction between them.

When the temperature is above the critical sterility point (CSP) of 32 °C for Nongken 58S, pollens become sterile; when temperature is below the critical fertility point (CFP) of 22 °C for Nongken 58S, pollens become fertile regardless of the photoperiod length. Photoperiod-

sensitive fertility can be induced in the temperature range from CSP to CFP (TRPS). Only in TRPS is the pollen fertility alteration of PGMS regulated by photoperiod conditions. Even within TRPS, however, temperature conditions can still affect critical light length (CLL) and the degree of fertility alteration: when CLL becomes shorter, fertility decreases under short-day conditions as the temperature rises; when CLL becomes longer, fertility increases under short-day conditions as the temperature decreases.

The conditions for the sterility gene expression and the intensity of interaction between photoperiod and temperature differ among male sterile lines. Those

conditions determine whether a line is adaptable and can be used in rice production. CFP causes sterility fluctuation under long-day conditions. If the CFP of a sterile line being used in hybrid seed production is not low enough, a low temperature may cause it to self-fertilize. If the CSP is not high enough, it is very difficult to multiply the sterile line in short-day seasons under high temperature conditions.

CLL and the intensity of the interaction effect between photoperiod and temperature control the adaptability of a line. A line with a longer CLL could be used in high latitudes and a line with a shorter CLL could be used in low latitudes. A line with a larger interaction

Spikelet fertility % of PGMS rice under various conditions.

Temp (°C)	Fertility (%) at given daylength (h:min)						
	13:00	13:20	13:40	14:00	14:20	14:40	15:00
<i>Nongken 58S583^a (japonica, photoperiod-sensitive)</i>							
22	25.4	23.8	21.6	19.1	24.6	26.5	24.7
24	61.8	57.7	43.5	24.6	18.5	7.9	1.7
26	54.6	45.9	32.1	7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
28	42.8	32.7	12.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
30	21.5	12.3	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>6334S^a (japonica, photoperiod-sensitive)</i>							
22	29.6	24.1	21.8	21.8	26.7	25.3	23.8
24	57.5	43.8	36.6	26.5	17.6	11.0	5.6
26	53.6	42.4	23.8	7.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
28	34.7	25.1	10.6	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
30	11.9	8.6	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>W7415S^b (indica, photoperiod-insensitive)</i>							
22	16.4	15.8	21.2	18.5	18.5	21.6	17.6
24	43.3	38.6	25.6	23.7	25.8	23.8	24.7
26	34.6	5.8	5.3	4.9	4.2	2.6	3.8
28	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>W6154S^b (indica, photoperiod-insensitive)</i>							
22	19.4	16.9	17.9	21.5	21.8	23.0	19.5
24	56.8	49.5	29.6	27.8	30.6	28.5	28.7
26	43.2	24.8	15.4	20.1	17.9	12.8	16.4
28	1.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2
<i>Mudanjiang 8 (check 1, japonica)</i>							
22	37.4	35.8	41.9	41.2	42.3	42.9	42.0
24	67.9	65.9	71.2	74.2	67.9	67.5	64.3
26	67.6	64.6	64.9	70.2	67.9	65.3	64.0
28	65.4	65.9	71.0	65.4	66.8	54.9	61.8
30	51.8	50.7	49.6	46.7	43.5	41.8	40.6
32	32.3	31.9	29.7	27.5	25.9	24.6	24.7
34	6.5	3.7	3.2	2.8	2.2	1.9	1.4
<i>Guangluai 4 (check 2, indica)</i>							
22	25.4	25.9	27.9	30.4	31.8	32.5	31.3
24	56.8	54.5	53.9	56.8	54.2	57.8	57.2
26	72.0	76.3	7.4	68.9	70.6	71.0	71.5
28	67.9	67.4	71.9	75.3	68.5	68.1	65.4
30	56.8	61.5	54.3	53.8	51.0	50.6	48.4
32	42.9	42.0	39.6	35.6	38.7	34.7	32.5
34	7.4	5.7	4.3	4.8	5.2	2.3	2.8

^a Values were zero at 32 and 34 °C. ^b Values were zero at 30, 32, and 34 °C.